

Parametric Architecture for Minimizing Extreme Heat and Solar Radiation in Building: Case Studies and Experimental Modelling

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ABSTRACT

Climate change and associated extreme heat challenges require holistic effort towards developing innovative design for a more resilient and sustainable urban environment. This study explores the potential of Parametric Architecture (PA) as a tool for minimizing the extreme solar radiation and heat challenges in Nigeria. The research adopts a two-pronged approach. First, exploratory case studies showcasing successful implementations of parametric design in some of the world's climatic regions. Second, an experimental case was undertaken involving an innovative design approach that employs parametric algorithms to dynamically generate and manipulate architectural forms using weather data of Akure, Nigeria. The study reveals the potential of PA's kinetic facades for adaptive architecture leveraging sunlight mimicking. This research contributes to the growing knowledge on PA as it lays the groundwork for future works. The study demonstrates the potentials of PA for creating a more resilient and sustainable urban environment.

Keywords: Daylighting, Energy Efficiency, Parametric Tools, Sustainability, Algorithm

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INTRODUCTION

There is increasing evidence that climate change is resulting in rising heat waves and building overheating leading to low productivity and health risks for occupants (Hampo et al., 2024). In combating the sustainability issue in built environment, parametric architecture has become top priority. Parametric Architecture (PA) is the computation design and algorithms that analyzes solar angles and wind patterns (Hudson, 2015). It is a performance-related design solution to building design issues particularly energy efficiency (Nasir and Kamal, 2023). It is a tool that assists to minimize solar heat gain and maximize natural ventilation.

Parametric design tools such as Grasshopper, Rhinoceros, Diva and Galapagos allow designers to define parameters and adjust variables that directly influence building performance outcomes (Ahmad et al., 2025; Saleh & Hegazy, 2023; Fang & Cho, 2019). Key features embedded in the application of these tools include

building orientation for maximizing solar gain, window-to-wall ratios for balancing daylight and heat gain, structural member dimensions for load-bearing capacity, space layout and circulation for user's comfort and accessibility. Different from traditional design approach which require time-consuming analysis on energy efficiency, solar radiation etc, PA enables quick analysis of large design parameters required for optimizing building features and efficiency. For instance, PA could enable design of venetian blinds that automatically adjust to sun movement based on an algorithm (Ieracitano et al., 2022; Nicholetti et al. 2023). PA is gaining fast prominence in architecture due to its potential for energy saving and lighting efficiency ((Michelle & Gemilang, 2022; Ahmad et al, 2025; Lou et al. 2025).

Studies (Fang & Cho, 2019, Ieracitano et al., 2022; Ikudayisi et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2025) have reiterated several significant advantages of the PA iteration process in building designs. PA has enabled design performance; support repetitive tasks, innovative design form and sustainability (Alkhatib et al. 2022; Ikudayisi et al., 2022; Bhandari et al., 2024). Specifically, the use of parametric design tools' enables real time data modification in design iterations analysis, allowing for adjustments based on changing climatic conditions (Lou et al., 2025). PA offers flexibility in design process and enhances the resilience of buildings to adapt to future needs or unforeseen circumstances.

Scholars are increasingly investigating multi-objective optimization (MOO) for improving architectural design based on PA tools. For instance, Lou et al. (2025) explore PA algorithms for low and zero-energy optimization. Using EVoM and Grasshopper platforms, a 26.89% performance improvement was achieved on solar radiation effect minimization while daylighting was also enhanced by 19.85%. Zhang et al. (2016) used PA for optimizing building geometry in China. The study revealed PA's potential for maximizing solar radiation gain, maximizing spatial efficiency, and minimizing the shape factor. Similarly, Konis et al. (2016) optimized a building geometry considering factors such as daylighting, passive solar energy use, and natural ventilation in the US using PA tools. The optimized design confirms that energy use intensity could be minimized by 4–17%, while daylighting performance could improve by 27–65%.

Wu et al. (2022) adopted PA for achieving zero energy across different climatic zones of China. The result shows that PA tools are useful for developing energy-saving policies and standards towards optimizing residential living, energy saving, and economy. Liu et al. (2023) used Rhino and Grasshopper in the design of a library with a view of optimizing modular system in the simulated data. The result highlights the role of PA in making building orientation decision, improving daylighting performance, and overall architectural quality. Eltaweel & Yuehong (2017) systematic review shows the enormous potentials of parametric tools for optimization of building facades for solar energy capture and significant reduction in energy consumption.

In Nigeria as elsewhere in Africa, the potential of PA is yet to be well harnessed towards developing climate-resilient and sustainable urban communities. Studies remain scanty on the adoption of PA for

innovative design and solving climate-related challenges. This study fills the gap as it presents design experimentation via simulations for optimal solutions for mitigating solar radiation in buildings. This study provides an evidence-based investigation on the role of PA in reduction of extreme heat and solar radiation in buildings based on Nigeria's climatic context.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on case study and experimental study of parametric design in sustainable built environment in architectural field in responses to the global climatic conditions.

Case Study

Exploratory case study approach was employed using five (5) buildings that exhibits exceptional outcomes of PA. These buildings were selected across different climatic regions in order to understand the variations and the how these projects achieved the sustainability goals. The building analyzed are

- i. Heydar Aliyev Center, Baku in Azerbaijan,
- ii. One Central Park, Sydney, Australia,
- iii. The CCTV Headquarters, Beijing, China,
- iv. The Al Bahar Towers, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- v. The Interlace, Singapore

The key design features assessed include the physical structure properties, orientation, shape, lighting, and energy factors. These buildings represent the best architectural master piece and foremost sustainable buildings with successful implementations of parametric design.

Experimental Modelling Using Algorithmic Control

The second aspect of this study entails an experimental modelling based on algorithm control. Algorithms are set of instructions used to generate models (Tedeschi, 2018). It incorporates traceability and allows the user to identify the parts of the algorithm by its iterative procedure called the isomorphic of the model (Caetano, Santos, & Leitão, 2020). The iterative process provides a finer degree of control, that facilitates debugging while maintain tasks that allows for changing of the variables or parameters. This study employed the weather file extracted from Energyplus, a building energy simulation program developed by the U.S. Department of Energy. It is widely used for predicting a building's energy consumption and thermal performance. EnergyPlus entails hourly data on various weather parameters and sunlight map for the region with detailed weather description files, known as EnergyPlus Weather (EPW). Grasshopper was used to set algorithm (Figure 1) for a pre-determined building parameter changes in iterations through moving the sliders of the parameters and achieving the manipulating features of the building. The parametric algorithms were used to dynamically generate and manipulate architectural forms using extracted data from Energyplus weather file for Akure, Nigeria. The typical format of the iterated process and the visual results of the design of the building is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Grasshopper Algorithm to Control Design Variables

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Figure 2: Algorithm Blowout for Thread and Riser

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Case Study of Parametric Modeled Buildings

CASE 1: Heydar Aliyev Center, Baku, Azerbaijan

Heydar Aliyev Center (Figure 3) designed by Zaha Hadid in 2012 demonstrates the impact of parametric design as an effective tool to develop sustainable building shape (De Boni, 2018). The building design incorporated parameters such as physical structure properties, lighting, and energy factors in its parametric modeling. The design approach and simulation reflected overall sustainability and energy efficient design of the Heydar Aliyev Centre.

Figure 3: Pictures showing different views of Heydar Aliyev Building

Source: De Boni, (2018)

With respect to its algorithm iterative modeling, the shape was adjusted for optimum conditions in artificial lighting and natural ventilation. The curve shapes of the facade helped the natural light rays to be clicked, dispersed and penetrated deeply into the building thus minimized the use of artificial lights at the day time. This aligns with the work of Ahmad et al. (2025) about parametric optimization of lighting achieved through shading surface of building in arid climate. Similarly, the parametric design process of Heydar Aliyev

Center paved way for proper positioning of building structure. This is evident in the structural system that allows for efficient management of the energy loads while minimizing the support demands and material usage. This was a key benefit derived from the parametric modeling process as identified by De Boni, (2018).

The enclosure of the building skin ensured optimization of utilization of surface as insulation properties for energy efficient glazing systems. The shape and inclination of the surface permits efficient harvesting and control of rain water. Though non portable, the water served mainly irrigational and other purposes and reduces the use of water in the building. This finding was regarded by Nasir and Kamal (2023) as inclusive strategies in the exploration of the role of parametric architecture in building design. The parametric design of process reveals efficiency in terms of the structural and facades of the building, use of the materials employed in the construction of the building that allows for sustainable energy practices.

CASE 2: One Central Park, Sydney, Australia

The One Central Park (Figure 4) built in Sydney, Australia reflects the use of parametric design for sustainability and urbanism purpose. This residential complex was designed by French architect Jean Nouvel to meet sustainable and energy efficient building needs (Nouvel & Beissel, 2014). The building shape externals has sequence of some curvilinear shapes and forms created using the technique of parametric design which helps in natural lighting and fresh air. Inclusion of green walls are significant feature of the towers for built-in vertical gardens and green façade. This supports the work of Ikudayisi et al. (2022) on integrated design process of green building projects for sustainable environment. The vertical gardens act as thermal insulating layer, an air filtration system and helps to reduce urban heat island effect. The parametric design approach enhanced surface design options for optimized building's internal natural light penetration as reported by Fang and Cho (2019) in their study on design optimization for daylighting and energy performance. Specifically, the modelling permits refinement of sheetlike planes, along with articulation of concave/convex forms to admit daylight deep into the building, with less heat gain and glare, requiring less artificial lighting and air conditioning.

Figure 4: One Central Park Building

Source: Nouvel and Beissel. (2014)

The parametric modeling allowed choosing the most suited form of building for natural ventilation. The principle of cross ventilation was applied on the exterior design of the building fabric such that patterns, forms of facades and openings minimize the usage of mechanical air condition systems. Optimal thermal performance of the building was achieved leveraging elements like glazed façade with energy efficient systems, improved insulation and renewable energy using the form of photo voltaic system. The complex geometries of the building's facade and landscaping were designed to accommodate efficient water capture techniques and management. Parametric modeling in the construction of One Central Park helped in the efficient use of materials, manipulation of complex forms and patterns with overall environmental impact of the building.

CASE 3: The CCTV Headquarters, Beijing, China

The CCTV Building in Beijing, China designed by architects Rem Koolhaas and Ole Scheeren of the Office for Metropolitan Architecture (OMA) is a practical example of parametric design in sustainable buildings (West & Coad, 2020). This structure clearly demonstrates how parametric design enables architectural skin responsiveness and efficiency. The shape of building created using parametric elements introduced features such as natural light, air conditioning, and energy in the architectural design process (Figure 5). Insights on the contribution of parametric design to the sustainability of CCTV Headquarters include the adjustment of the shape of the building's envelope with respect to lighting and natural ventilation; the loop structure made with continuous arrangements of openings timed to allow natural light into the building thus eliminating artificial lighting during the day. The optimized parametric model enhances the heating and cooling system with integral design solutions ranging from highly-performing glazing systems and insulation materials.

Figure 5: The CCTV Headquarters in Beijing

Source: West and Coad, 2020

The process of parametric modelling that incorporates natural ventilation called the chimney effect shows less mechanical systems. This justifies the use of PA in building geometry and structural layout at design stage according to Fang and Cho (2019). The choice of the continuous loop form reduced material wastage while structural members enhanced the utilization of all available material. This approach applied efficient geometrical disposition of the architectural structure in the CCTV Headquarters.

CASE 4: The Al Bahar Towers, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

The Al Bahar Tower is a twin tower built by Aedas Architects (Attia, 2017). It depicts energy efficient and environmental-friendly building developed using parametric design tools. A unique feature is the array of geometric shapes that changes its angles according to the direction of the sun (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Al Bahar Towers

Source: Attia, 2017

The kinetic façade system controls and maximizes light, solar rise, and energy consumption. The most defining factor in the use of parametric design is the dynamic operation of screen of thousands of small units that folds when the sun rises, affording indoor shading and reducing overheating as observed in this

architectural design. This supports the findings of Xuereb (2014) on the adaptive system in cooling load and air conditioning usage of the building. The impact is seen in the facade system which simultaneously gets the maximum effects of the daylight and the minimum of the glare real time. The interplay of geometric designs, double skin surface, and the motion of the facade units modulates light having less use of artificial lights during the day. This indicates less energy use in Al Bahar towers compared to other typical buildings in the Middle East. The reference to natural ventilation, integration of traditional elements with modern technology demonstrates the adaptability of parametric design in creating contextually responsive architecture as displayed in this architectural design is line with the findings of Ahmad et al. (2025).

CASE 5: The Interlace, Singapore

The Interlace building (Figure 7) is a residential architectural piece developed with parametric modeling in Singapore (Botti, 2023). Interlace was designed by Ole Scheeran conceptualizes energy sensitive structures that are responsive to sustainable environment. The parametric modeling iterative process delivers the building's stacked and interlocked design of multiple residential unit blocks. The residential layout showcases the sequence of the open yards, and the complex interweaving of the blocks with the help of the cantilevers controls and enhances the flow of natural ventilation.

Figure 7: The Interlace Residential Complex in Singapore

Source: Bott, (2023)

The parametric modeling appropriates setting of blocks in slight overlaps that optimize the site area, generate shared outdoor areas and internal gardens essential to the sustainable built environment. Similar to the findings of Nicoletti et al. (2023), optimization of structures with artificial neural networks achieved energy savings and visual comfort. The parametric design strategy allowed for optimization of the use of materials, insulations in solar systems thereby reducing loads on earth. It was also feasible that landscaping features interconnected with bridges offer chances for creation of green zones and consequently manufacturing of a favorable microclimate and other environmental aspects. The Interlace building deep dive into the application of parametric design tools for sustainable architecture within the environmental context.

Experimental Modelling and Algorithmic Building Facade

In an attempt to assess rising heat waves and glaring sunbaked buildings, the experimental study was carried out in Akure Ondo State. The experiment aims to investigate the dynamism and adaptability of sunshine variable within local context. The simulated sunlight data extracted from Energyplus online database for the study area unleash buildings integration with the environment creating spaces that respond to the sun's ever-changing path. Rhino and Grasshopper design tools were employed to construct the building model and design the kinetic facade with specific movement capabilities as shown in Figure 8, 9, and 10. Grasshopper's scripting language was used to create algorithms that govern the facade's dynamic responses, translating environmental data into managed physical actions.

The results show that solar-responsive parametric design of the facades change automatically to cut 20% of solar heat gain, saving energy and promoting comfortable, sunlit interiors. Similar findings from Fang and Cho (2019) revealed optimized designs in daylight performance by rhinoceros (38.7%) and grasshopper (31.6%) and also reduction in energy consumption by 20.2% and 18.5%, respectively. Similarly, the significant impact of parametric design towards solar heat minimization in hot climates like Akure was revealed through the models. This buttressed the findings of Ahmad et al. (2025) that PA modeling tools such as Rhino and Grasshopper can be used for optimized shading system reduces total radiation by 19% and cooling energy use gadgets by 26.2%.

Figure 8: Parametric building model using Rhino/Grasshopper for Akure

Source: Authors own work, 2025

Figure 9: Close view of kinetic façade for Akure

Figure 10: Algorithm generating the Parametric tower model with Kinetic Façade using Grasshopper
Source: Authors own work, 2025

Outcome of Akure Solar Data Integration and Simulation

The Ladybug, a Grasshopper plugin, was used to integrate real-world solar data for Akure, Ondo State. The interface (Figure 11) and simulated sunlight data as shown in Figure 12 accurately adjusts surface form and orientation in real-time, optimizing factors like, thermal comfort to reducing solar heat gain, cooler interiors, maximizes natural light while minimizing glare for improved environmental conditions. This aligns with Nicholetti et al., (2023) which revealed that the output provided by the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) showed target angle offer high reliability for windows with different orientation with energy savings for heating/cooling are up to 37.7 % and 38.7 %.

Figure 11: InteFrface of Energy plus

Source: Authors own work, 2025

Figure 12: Grasshopper Algorithm to Integrate Weather File

Source: Authors own work, 2025

The adjustment of sunlight features in the kinetic facade brought to fore two major outcomes which include firstly, moderation of interior temperature by the reduction of solar heat gain is beneficial to occupant's comfort and health, secondly, maximization of natural lighting through reduction in glare increase cost efficiency in energy consumption. The findings demonstrate profound use of parametric design's capacity for sustainability and user-centricity heat control. The design tools employed namely rhino and grasshopper presented an empirical, accessible and reproducible pathway for simulation of sunlight data in Akure.

CONCLUSION

The study investigates the potentials of PA for producing dynamic and responsive structures that meets sustainability goals using case studies and algorithm tools. The five case studies namely Heydar Aliyev Center, One Central Park, The CCTV Headquarters, The Al Bahar Towers, and The Interlace reveals the unique PA sustainability features including structural mining of shapes and forms, use of natural cooling for energy reduction, minimization of construction waste from pollutants and material efficiency gained through series of iteration procedure. The case studies outline resilience strategies for integration in building structure leveraging innovative and environmentally friendly architecture designs.

The PA experimentation method employed presents a pathway for simulation of sunlight data. The analysis reveals significant reduction of solar heat gain and maximization of natural lighting which potentially provides cost efficiency in energy consumption. The analysis offers a valuable perspective and demonstrates profound use of PA for climate-resilience and heat control in Nigeria's context. However, further research is required to expand knowledge in this domain. PA algorithm can be experimented on

other climate variables such as wind and humidity. In practice, it is imperative for professionals to explore the potential of PA tools for developing energy-saving and innovative building geometry. The prospect of PA for policies and standards development should be harnessed towards optimizing users' comfort, building aesthetics, energy saving, and design economy.

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